

FOOD, CULTURE AND IDENTITY

SERVICE DESIGN TOOLS AND METHODS IN A SOCIO-CULTURAL CONTEXT

Heidi Uppa, Marja Seliger, Tania Rodriguez-Kaarto
Aalto University, School of Arts, Design and Architecture
✉ heidi.uppa@aalto.fi, marja.seliger@aalto.fi, tania.rodriguez.garcia@aalto.fi

ABSTRACT

This full day workshop combines different aspects around local food culture and understanding food as a social bond between individuals and groups. The participants will contribute with their food related thoughts, ideas and experiences. They will learn about local food cultures by sharing their food-related stories, memories, emotions, ideas and rituals with each other. In the workshop, service design-related design game methods and tools will be tested in a food context and in a different cultural environment than originally designed for. The presumption is that local solutions are required to solve global problems such as food sustainability. We argue that understanding social identities and values are needed for the creation and appliance of new sustainable food concepts and services. This workshop explores social, emotional and cultural aspects of local food and how food related rituals, memories and tastes bring people together.

KEYWORDS: *food, culture, identity, design, social*

INTRODUCTION

Food sufficiency and sustainability have become one of the major environmental and ecological issues today; a global problem with no simple solutions. Local actions and understanding cultures and identities are needed for offering healthy and sustainable food options in the future. Food is a necessity with important social and cultural aspects. Food traditions play a role in our identity creation process (Gronow 1997) and eating can be seen as a social ritual bonding people together. However, the social aspects of food are not always recognized. In this workshop, service design methods and visual communication tools are used to explore the complexity of the subject and to gain a deeper knowledge and understanding about local food in a social context. This workshop explores how game design methods based on storytelling and narratives are adapted in different cultural environments. The aim is to offer new food related experiences and to gain a deeper understanding about how service design and participatory methods, tools and elements work in different cultural and social contexts.

WORKSHOP GOAL

The aim of the workshop is to test service design related methods and tools in a food culture context. “Identity map” and

“Food concept/Meal design” design games will be used to inspire participants to share their stories, memories, emotions, rituals and values related to food. Participants will learn new aspects of local Colombian food culture(s) as well as understand their own food-related behavior and emotions. They will gain knowledge and experience about service design and participatory methods while interacting with other participants from different cultures and backgrounds.

One goal of the workshop is to test the qualities of the chosen design games and tools and to evaluate how the game concepts, formats and mechanics work in a new context. Using design games as a research method is becoming common and therefore it is important to test their applicability in different cultural and social environments. The crucial question is the validity of the design game concepts and how to develop or adjust them for different cultural contexts. The aim is to learn more about good game facilitation and share the knowledge with the participants.

PREVIOUS STUDIES

This workshop combines elements from design thinking, visual communication, semiotics, service design, game design, social psychology and self-categorization theories (Turner, Hogg, Oakes, Reicher, & Wetherell, 1987). Some previous

research related to consumer behavior in the field of branding and marketing can also be found. This workshop proposal is based on experiences and research done by organizers in the Shape-Sustainable Meal project, which focused on providing sustainable design solutions for lunch caterers in Finland. More info: <http://gdresearch.aalto.fi/site/research/sustainable-meal-communication>

WORKSHOP DETAILS

Length of the workshop: Full day (6 hours)

Location: Cali

Participants: Maximum 24 and minimum 12 participants can be accepted

Requirements for the venue:

- a room large enough for 12–24 people
- tables and chairs to work on (groups of 4–6 people)
- electricity, power bars and cables (for laptops)
- a projector and wall/screen to project on
- access to the internet
- ideally the venue would be close to some local restaurants or food market

All other materials (paper, posters, cards, pens, objects, stickers) will be provided by the workshop organizers. Contact details: Heidi Uppa, heidi.uppa@aalto.fi

Participation

Participants should have an interest in art, design or design research, but no other specific professional or educational experience is required. However, we hope that participants will share a passion for food and culture. Participants are encouraged to bring visual materials (photos, pictures) to the workshop. The materials should be related to their eating habits, memories or cultural traditions.

WORKSHOP SCHEDULE (TENTATIVE)

Full-day workshop with the following schedule outline:

AM: Introduction and Identification Tool

- Introduction to the workshop aims, activities and the schedule.
- Inspirational introduction lecture on “food, culture and identity”.

- Grouping: formation of groups of 4–6 people.
- Group work, part 1: sketching exercise to introduce group members to each other.
- Group work, part 2: discussions about personal eating habits, values and beliefs related to food.
Documentation by using “self identification map” tool.
- Group work, part 3: Idea creation session and choosing a subject for the group exercise by using identification maps. Collection of possible additional materials and visual references for the exercise. Active exploration of the subject.

Lunch Break

(can also be used for material collection and to explore the subject)

PM: Game Session and Presentations

- Group work, part 4: “food concept/meal design” game session.
- Presentations by the groups of their results and insights.
- Final discussions and feedback

AFTER THE WORKSHOP

The organizers will produce a summary of the workshop reflecting the discussions, materials and learning outcomes. The format, contents, distribution and the platform of the summary will be decided in the workshop.

REFERENCES

- Gronow, J. (1997). *Sociology of Taste*. London: Routledge.
- Hall, S. (ed.) (1997). *Representation. Cultural Representations and Signifying Practices*. London: Sage.
- Lawson, B. (2004). *What designers know*. Architectural Press.
- Sennett, R. (2012). *Together. The Rituals, Pleasures and Politics of Cooperation*, London: Allen Lane
- Stickdorn, M. and Schneider J. (2012). *This is Service Design Thinking*. Amsterdam: Bis Publishers
- Turner, J. C., Hogg, M. A., Oakes, P. J., Reicher, S. D., & Wetherell, M. S. (1987). *Rediscovering the Social Group. A Self-categorization Theory*. New York: Blackwell.
- Vaajakallio, K. (2012). *Design Games as a Tool, a Mindset, and a Structure*. Aalto University publication series, Doctoral dissertations 87/2012, School of Arts, Design and Architecture, Finland.